

Title: Scripting and monitoring meet each other: aligning learning analytics and learning design to support teachers in orchestrating CSCL situations

Authors:

María Jesús Rodríguez-Triana, Alejandra Martínez-Monés, Juan I. Asensio-Pérez, Yannis Dimitriadis

Email: (chus@gsic, amartine@infor, juaase@tel, yannis@tel).uva.es

GSIC-EMIC, Universidad de Valladolid, Spain (<http://www.gsic.uva.es>)

Abstract:

From the conceptualization to the evaluation of CSCL scenarios, teachers address multiple tasks, sometimes being overwhelmed on account of the required time and associated burden. To support teachers in this endeavor, we propose to connect the pedagogical decisions made at design time with the analysis of the participants' interactions. Thus, teachers would be provided with relevant and coarse-grained information that could help them manage their CSCL scenarios at run-time. This paper synthesizes the main contributions obtained from a 3-year DBR process, and presents the findings obtained from the evaluation of the current proposal in 2 authentic CSCL scenarios. The participant teachers valued the proposal positively and stated that it was helpful for their orchestration of CSCL scenarios.

1. Introduction

Among the multiple concerns and tasks involved in the orchestration of Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning (CSCL) scenarios (Dillenbourg, Nussbaum, Dimitriadis, & Roschelle, 2013), many are oriented to foster effective collaboration. Several strategies may be adopted to support collaboration, assuming either a Learning Design (LD) or a Learning Analytics (LA) perspective (Jermann, Soller, & Lesgold, 2004). In LD approaches, scripting defines, before the interaction begins, the sequence of learning tasks, resources, and scaffolds that the students will need throughout the learning situation. From a LA perspective, monitoring analyzes students' interactions at run-time, and facilitates the intervention on the situation towards a more productive direction.

Although these strategies help teachers in the orchestration of CSCL scenarios, there are still outstanding problems. Despite scripting the learning scenario beforehand, eventualities may emerge at run-time and jeopardize the initial plan. Furthermore, even if the analysis of the students' interactions generates useful insights on how the learning process unfolds, the information that current monitoring proposals provide to the teachers is not always easy to interpret (Dyckhoff, Lukarov, Muslim, Chatti, & Schroeder, 2013). Thus, teachers often lack relevant information to eventually intervene and adapt their plans at run-time.

Several researchers point out the potential synergies that may be derived from aligning both strategies (Lockyer, Heathcote, & Dawson, 2013), eg., providing teachers with analyses connected to the pedagogical decisions described in design-time. Indeed, this approach has been applied in combination with e-portfolios (Reimann & Mayer, 2013) and on-line simulators (Lejeune & Guéraud, 2012). Although these proposals are good examples of the benefits of the aforementioned alignment approach, they have a limited applicability, being restricted to a single learning platform and to a specific assessment approach.

Our proposal's main objective is to **provide teachers with design and management support capable of linking their pedagogical intentions and run-time information needs, by aligning scripting and monitoring strategies**. Instead of focusing on a single learning platform and assessment approach (as the aforementioned solutions do), our proposal is oriented to CSCL scenarios supported by Distributed Learning Environments (DLEs), which are becoming increasingly popular in current pedagogical practice.

DLEs integrate existing learning platforms (eg. mainstream Virtual Learning Environments such as Moodle or Sakai) with external tools (typically, Web 2.0 tools such as wikis, blogs or Google applications). Using DLEs makes designing and managing the learning process even more challenging.

Towards this main objective, we have followed a Design-Based Research (DBR) approach involving 3 iterations, encompassing 7 studies in authentic CSCL scenarios with 5 different teachers. While the first and second iterations were mainly exploratory, the third one focused on the evaluation of the main contributions that emerged during the previous iterations: **a monitoring-aware design process and model**, and a **script-aware monitoring process**. In this paper, we focus on this third iteration, presenting the current version and evaluation of these contributions. Previous, non-finalised versions of these proposals along this DBR process were already reported elsewhere (Rodríguez-Triana, Martínez-Monés, Asensio-Pérez, & Dimitriadis, 2013a) (Rodríguez-Triana, Martínez-Monés, Asensio-Pérez, & Dimitriadis, 2013b).

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of CSCL research that addresses scripting and the analysis of participants' interactions; Section 3 describes the research methodology; Sections 4 and 5 introduce and evaluate the contributions respectively; finally, conclusions and future work are summarised in Section 6.

2. Related work

CSCL scripts are scaffolds that structure and constrain the way students are expected to interact when learning collaboratively using (although not necessarily) technology. More specifically, CSCL macro-scripts describe coarse-grained collaborative learning pedagogical methods that typically include a sequence of activities in which a set of groups, roles and resources are involved (Kollar, Fischer, & Hesse, 2006) (Dillenbourg & Tchounikine, 2007) (Weinberger, Kollar, Dimitriadis, Mäkitalo-Siegl, & Fischer, 2009). Designing CSCL macro-scripts ('scripts' hereinafter) has been recognized as a key aspect for the orchestration of CSCL scenarios: CSCL practitioners can anticipate during the design process of their scripts contextual issues of their classroom (technological, social, timing,... and also awareness needs) that may require subsequent orchestration interventions (Dillenbourg et al., 2013).

Orchestration interventions in response to unexpected events heavily depend on the awareness of what is happening. Learning Analytics can thus be considered as an important orchestration aid of great importance, especially when using non-trivial technological settings. In the particular case of CSCL, monitoring students' interactions (mediated or not by technology) plays a crucial role, since such interactions are the main drivers of the collaborative learning process. Existing models of technology-mediated interactions typically include: participating peers, groups, roles, resources and actions (Miao, Hoeksema, Hoppe, & Harrer, 2005) (Harrer, Martínez-Monés, & Dimitracopoulou, 2009). Current data gathering and analysis proposals can be classified in two main coarse-grained sets. Data-driven approaches (Mitra, Pal, & Mitra, 2002) (Dron & Anderson, 2009) (Chatti, Dyckhoff, Schroeder, & Thüs, 2012) generate indicators describing the collaboration process in a bottom-up fashion, based on available data. Conversely, model-driven approaches (Soller, Martínez-Monés, Jermann, & Muehlenbrock, 2005) need pre-specified models of expected collaborative interactions that guide the monitoring data gathering and analysis in a top-down process. Such pre-specified models should be closely linked with the pedagogical intentions of the designed CSCL scenario.

All in all, current work on CSCL orchestration recognizes the need for aligning scripting and monitoring. However, few proposals make this alignment explicit throughout lifecycle of design, technological deployment, run-time/management, and evaluation/assessment of CSCL scenarios. Such alignment

would change the way CSCL scripts are designed by educators, as well as the way learning analytics data are collected from CSCL systems and subsequently analyzed for “closing the cycle”. The final goal is providing those educators with valuable awareness information that they can use, for orchestration purposes or reflection material about the effectiveness of the enacted script.

3. Research methodology

The complex, evolving nature of our research goal (aligning scripting and monitoring to support teachers in designing and managing CSCL scenarios) led us to employ a DBR approach. The research process comprised three iterations (two exploratory and an evaluative one, see Figure 1). The two first iterations led to the definition and refinement of the proposals (presented in their current status in Section 4): a monitoring-aware design process, an accompanying data model, and a script-aware monitoring process. These three proposals were evaluated in the third DBR iteration (scenarios labeled EV1 and EV2 in Figure 1). Section 5 shows the results of these two latter studies.

The 7 studies that make up our 3-iteration DBR were connected to 7 courses carried out at the University of Valladolid (Spain) between October 2010 and May 2013, involving 5 subjects, 5 teachers and a total of 365 students from 3 different degrees (“Telecommunication Engineering”, “Master’s Degree for Pre-service Secondary Education Teachers” and “Kindergarten education”). These scenarios present a common profile: blended CSCL scenarios interleaving face-to-face and computer-supported activities, mixture of individual and collaborative learning activities, developed both inside and outside the classroom, technologically supported by DLEs, and within a time frame between 2 and 4 weeks per scenario.

[Figure 1: Overview of the iterations and studies that constitute the DBR process]

4. Proposals

The first two iterations of our DBR process explored how to support teachers in aligning their pedagogical intentions and run-time information needs. During that exploratory phase we iteratively proposed two interdependent processes, named “monitoring-aware design process” and “script-aware monitoring process”, as well as a model for enhancing CSCL scripts with design-time decisions on monitoring issues, thus establishing the connections between the two processes. This section presents the final version of these three contributions.

4.1. Monitoring-aware design process

This process describes the steps that teachers, acting as CSCL script designers, should follow during the design of CSCL scenarios, in order to reflect on their monitoring needs and express their expectations about students’ interactions.

Figure 2 shows the monitoring-aware design process (Rodríguez-Triana et al., 2013a), which is based on the pattern-based design process defined by Villasclaras-Fernández, Hernández-leo, Asensio-Pérez, & Dimitriadis (2009). The proposed process identifies and makes the design decisions that could eventually affect monitoring explicit: the pattern(s) that the script implements -if any-, the activity flow, the configuration of each activity and group, and the resources and tools to be used in the scenario. The process comprises two cycles. The first one, Monitoring-aware design cycle, guides script designers in identifying basic constraints to be monitored regarding activities, groups and resources. Then, the Monitoring enhancement cycle extends the script with new data gathering and/or monitoring support

activities. These extensions should be scaffolded on the basis of the data sources concerning the constraints to be monitored (eg. ICT supports tools but also students, teachers and even observers).

[Figure 2: Monitoring-aware design process of CSCL scripts. Stars point out steps with monitoring-related tasks. Red elements, preceded by (c1), refer to the first cycle, and blue elements, preceded by (c2), refer the second cycle]

4.2. *Monitoring-aware scripting model*

This model specifies the script elements to be provided by teachers (acting as script designers) after completing the “monitoring-aware design process” (Rodríguez-Triana et al., 2013a). The proposal draws on scripting and interaction analysis models mentioned in Section 2, but also incorporates information about design-time decisions that could eventually affect run-time monitoring, as elicited during the exploratory iterations of the DBR process (see Figure 3). We have classified these design-time decisions into 3 dimensions:

- Pedagogical Pattern and/or general script constraints: dependencies between activities (eg. sequencing or resources reuse), collaboration and group formation policies.
- Activity constraints: deadlines, resources and tools assigned to each activity, participants, groups, social level (individually or in groups), interactivity types (face-to-face, through computers or blended), presentiality (face-to-face, distance or blended) and participation (optional or mandatory)
- Teacher’s monitoring decisions: monitoring periods, elements (actions, activities and resources) to be monitored, and expected use of resources (eg. optional or mandatory, individually or by groups).

[Figure 3: Monitoring-aware model of CSCL scripts]

4.3. *Script-aware monitoring process*

This so called script-aware monitoring process defines how the design-time pedagogical decisions captured in the script may guide run-time data gathering and analysis to provide teachers with relevant monitoring information (Rodríguez-Triana et al., 2013b).

Our proposal (see Figure 4) extends the collaboration analysis process of Soller et al. (2005). It is a model-driven approach for collaborative interaction analysis (see Section 2), thus requiring the definition of an ideal model of interaction prior to the actual monitoring.

The script-aware monitoring process has four steps. Step 1 uses the description of the learning activities of the CSCL script for collecting interaction data: for each activity, the involved participants’ interactions are gathered, taking into account the teachers monitoring preferences (resources and types of interaction to be monitored) and the activity deadlines. In Step 2, the desired model of interaction is built upon certain parameters of the script, as defined in the “monitoring-aware scripting model”: participation (involvement of an individual or group in the activity); collaboration (interactions among groups and/or group members); use of resources (interactions between participants and resources); group formation policies (requirements that groups should meet in terms of criteria such as size or type of participants); and activity flow dependencies (activity parameters that affect other activities, eg. reused resources, groups, or deadlines). In Step 3, actual (Step 1) versus ideal (Step 2) models of interaction are compared. In Step

4 teachers are informed about the alignment (or lack thereof) of the actual/ideal models of interaction. Finally, teachers interpret this output and intervene in the learning situation if needed.

[Figure 4: Script-aware monitoring process. The boxes represent the steps defined by Soller et al. (2005) and the descriptions in red explain how design-time script elements affect each step]

5. Evaluation

The main contributions presented in Section 4 were evaluated in two studies carried out in CSCL scenarios. This section introduces these two studies and presents the evaluation results.

5.1. Context and methodology

The evaluative studies (EV1 and EV2) involved two teachers with different levels of expertise in CSCL scenarios. The scenarios involved different sets of challenges that made them good candidates for the evaluation of the proposal: the first one involved a high number of students and resources; the second one presented a complex design, with many interrelated activities occurring in a short period of time. Figure 1 describes the scenarios in terms of number of students, activities and resources, as well as the tools that made up the DLE.

In both studies: first, we provided teachers with worksheets and forms to scaffold the “monitoring-aware design process”; second, the teacher used WebCollage to create a computational representation of the CSCL script, using GLUE!-PS (Group Learning Unified Environment - Pedagogical Scripting) to deploy the design into the DLE; third, the first author manually transformed the forms filled in by the teacher into an XML representation compliant with the “monitoring-aware model” of CSCL scripts; fourth, we automatically enforced the “script-aware monitoring process” using the GLIMPSE system (Group Learning Interaction Monitor for Pedagogical Scripting Environments). Interestingly, the GLUE!-CAS system (Collaboration Analysis Support for GLUE!) was used during Step 1 of the “script-aware monitoring process” for the gathering and integration of interaction data from the DLE (Rodríguez-Triana, Martínez-Monés, & Asensio-Pérez, 2011); finally, we provided the teachers with monitoring reports.

Figure 5 shows the data sources collected in both studies and the relation between these sources and the evaluative questions. The researcher interviewed the teachers at the beginning of the studies to collect the teachers’ common CSCL design and management strategies (documents labeled [EV1_INT1] and [EV2_INT1]). Then the researcher observed how the teachers carried out the design process (documents [EV1_R_OBS1] and [EV2_R_OBS1]) and gathered teachers’ impressions regarding the monitoring-aware design process and model through interviews ([EV1_INT2] and [EV2_INT2]). During the enactment, the teachers were asked to daily annotate all the eventualities that emerged during the learning scenarios, expressing their expectations about the monitoring reports before checking them, and notifying any errors detected ([EV1_T_OBS] and [EV2_T_OBS]). At the same time, the researcher observed the DLE ([EV1_R_OBS2] and [EV2_R_OBS2]) to verify that the data gathered from the technological infrastructure were coherent. Once the learning activity finished, the researcher interviewed teachers again, to collect their opinions on the script-aware monitoring process, and to evaluate the proposals as a whole ([EV1_INT3] and [EV2_INT3]).

[Figure 5: Connections between evaluative studies, evaluative questions and data sources]

5.2. Results

Below we discuss the evidence gathered from the studies, following the evaluative questions presented in Figure 5.

- a. EQ1: Does the monitoring-aware design process of CSCL scripts help teachers to align pedagogical and monitoring issues?

To answer this question, we needed to assess whether the proposed process was understandable and affordable for the teachers (in terms of the effort). We also needed to know whether the process allowed teachers to express their pedagogical intentions, and whether they perceived that the resulting design was enriched by the process.

Both teachers agreed that the process was coherent and easily understandable, and they perceived the monitoring aspects as an integral part of the design process [EV1_INT2][EV2_INT2]. Additionally, some suggestions emerged during the interviews to improve the flexibility of the process [EV2_INT2].

Regarding the costs and benefits of the design process, the EV1 required a total of 94 minutes [EV1_R_OBS1] and the EV2 108 minutes [EV2_R_OBS1]. Despite the time involved, the teachers did not identify a significant increment in the required effort [EV1_INT2][EV2_INT2], since they usually devote a comparable amount of time to design their scenarios [EV1_INT1][EV2_INT1].

The teachers confirmed that they could describe the scenarios as they had initially envisioned using the provided forms and tools [EV1_R_OBS1] [EV2_R_OBS2] [EV1_INT2] [EV2_INT2]. Nevertheless, the “monitoring-aware design process” encouraged the teachers to modify the scripts to better satisfy both pedagogical and monitoring needs [EV1_INT2][EV2_INT2].

In summary, according to the teachers’ comments, the monitoring-aware design process helped them to enrich the scripts, as well as to anticipate potential eventualities [EV1_INT2][EV2_INT2].

- b. EQ2: Does the monitoring-aware model of CSCL scripts allow expressing the scripting and monitoring aspects required to guide the monitoring process?

To address this question, it was necessary to evaluate the model in two directions: first, validating whether the model was understandable for teachers and satisfied teachers’ needs to express the design decisions; and second, verifying whether the model provided the details required by the monitoring process to guide the analysis in terms of the scripts.

The teachers confirmed that the model was expressive enough to represent the teachers’ pedagogical issues [EV1_INT1][EV2_INT1][EV1_INT2][EV2_INT2]. However, the teachers pointed out that some terms were difficult to interpret [EV1_INT2][EV2_INT2] or were ambiguous and required clarification [EV1_R_OBS1][EV2_R_OBS1].

Additionally, the information represented in the model allowed the GLIMPSE tool to automatically carry out the script-aware monitoring process in both scenarios [EV1_R_OBS2][EV2_R_OBS2].

- c. EQ3: Does the script-aware monitoring process provide teachers with relevant information for the management of the CSCL scenario?

To answer these questions, we firstly verified whether the information provided by the monitoring process was unknown, comprehensive and relevant for the teacher. Then, we evaluated whether the information reduced the effort invested in the management of the CSCL scenario.

Teachers were sometimes already aware of a part of the monitoring reports' information (eg. when the activities happened in the classroom or the students had contacted them to notify any problem) [EV1_T_OBS] [EV2_T_OBS][EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3]. However, both agreed that including this information in the reports helped them to keep the scenario in their minds [EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3].

According to the teachers, the information presented in the reports was useful to identify unexpected events, follow the learning activities, and better understand the student progress [EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3]. The teachers agreed that the monitoring reports reduced the time and effort devoted to managing the CSCL scenario [EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3], and emphasized three main reasons: (1) gathering and integrating the data from the different sources eliminated the need of going through all the documents involved in the scenarios-[EV1_INT1] [EV2_INT1]; (2) using the script constraints to guide and present the data analysis facilitated the interpretation of the monitoring reports [EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3]; (3) the potential problems detected helped the teachers to use more efficiently the time available for managing the learning scenario [EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3].

Despite the aforementioned benefits, there were some drawbacks such as false positives (one case in the EV2) [EV2_T_OBS] and unexpected events that went unnoticed (two cases in the EV1) [EV1_T_OBS]. Though the false positives did not represent a problem for the teacher [EV2_INT3], the eventualities that were not detected could have jeopardized the learning situation [EV1_INT3]. One potential solution is to triangulate the information retrieved from the technology with the students' and teachers' feedback; another is to include new indicators that filter or measure the quality of the students' interactions [EV1_INT3].

In addition, from the technological point of view, the script-aware monitoring process was implemented automatically by GLIMPSE. This fact shows that it is feasible to guide computationally the monitoring process by means of the parameters collected from the script.

d. Overall remarks

Looking at the proposal as a whole, the teachers highlighted that the alignment of pedagogical and monitoring issues had improved both the design and the management of the learning scenario [EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3]. They emphasized that the aforementioned proposals could contribute to facilitate the adoption of CSCL in authentic practice [EV1_INT3], especially if the scenario presents a moderate degree of complexity [EV1_INT3] [EV2_INT3].

6. Conclusions

Teachers orchestrating CSCL situations can benefit from the alignment between scripting and monitoring, two well-known approaches to LD and LA, respectively. This paper has presented our proposal of two interdependent processes: the "monitoring-aware design process" (together with the associated "monitoring-aware scripting model") and the "script-aware monitoring process", which exploit the synergies between LD and LA in CSCL settings. This paper also presents the evaluation of these contributions in two studies, which constitute the last cycle of a DBR process. The studies were carried out in learning scenarios with either a large number of students, or a complex collaborative activity flow. In both studies, data gathering, integration and analysis were supported by automatic means.

The results obtained from our evaluations show that the monitoring-aware design process and its underlying monitoring-aware scripting model were capable of supporting teachers in defining scripts enriched with monitoring information, which could be used by the script-aware monitoring process to provide informed feedback to the teachers. This feedback was meaningful and useful for the teachers to

manage the learning activities while they were taking place. Teachers also used this feedback to reflect post-hoc about the development of the courses, using this information to refine their future learning designs. In conclusion, both the monitoring-aware design process and the design-aware monitoring process successfully used monitoring information to support teachers in the design of CSCL situations.

The evaluation processes also helped identify minor issues which have been incorporated in the proposals, or that must be taken into account for future work. One major research line enabled by this work is the inclusion of new forms of feedback, based on higher-level learning analytics, enabling teachers to reflect on the learning outcomes of the students. This line of work will also be promoted by the automation of the design process in an existing authoring tool, which may enable teachers to perform the whole cycle without any aid from researchers.

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Figure 1: Overview of the iterations and studies that constitute the DBR process

Figure 2: Monitoring-aware design process of CSCL scripts. Stars point out steps with monitoring-related tasks. Red elements, preceded by (c1), refer to the first cycle, and blue elements, preceded by (c2), represent the second cycle

Figure 3: Monitoring-aware model of CSCL scripts

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Figure 5: Connections between evaluative studies, evaluative questions and data sources